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Cryptocurrency Transactions And Tax Compliance In Anambra State: An Accounting Perspective

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ABSTRACT

The study, while relying on primary and secondary data source, examined the impact of cryptocurrency transactions on tax compliance in Anambra State from an accounting perspective. Three research questions were formulated for the study and a corresponding three hypotheses. Research design for the study is the Descriptive survey research design and One Sample Mean Z-test was utilized for validating the three hypotheses formulated using SPSS Statistical software IBM 26. In determining the sample size of this study, the Taro Yamane formula for determining a sample size from a finite population was used. The study found a significant awareness and adoption of cryptocurrency transactions among individuals and businesses in Anambra State ($P < 0.05$). The study also found that there is a statistically significant challenge posed by crypto-currency transactions to tax authorities and accounting professionals in enforcing compliance ($P < 0.05$). Finally, the study found that existing tax policies and regulatory frameworks is effective in managing crypto-currency related transactions in Anambra State ($P < 0.05$). Consequent on the findings, the study recommended amongst others that there is need for continuous public enlightenment by regulatory authorities such as the Federal Inland Revenue Service (FIRS) and professional accounting bodies as that this will ensure that users and businesses are better informed about the tax implications, risks, and reporting obligations associated with cryptocurrency transactions.

Keywords: Crypto; Tax; Compliance; Transactions; Digitalization

1.0 INTRODUCTION

The widespread adoption of crypto-currencies have given rise to complex challenges for tax authorities and financial regulators across the globe. As decentralized digital assets continue to gain prominence within the global financial landscape, traditional regulatory frameworks, largely designed for centralized and easily traceable financial transactions are increasingly strained in their ability to effectively monitor, classify and tax these emerging instruments (Prabin, Prashamsa, Biplob & Nirmal, 2025).

This rapid proliferation has complicated issues such as transaction traceability, valuation consistency, jurisdictional authority, and compliance enforcement (Silva & Da Silva, 2022). The anonymous nature of many crypto-currency transactions further undermines the capacity of regulators to accurately assess taxable events and ensure adherence to existing tax laws. Consequently, governments and regulatory bodies are compelled to reconsider and adapt their policy approaches, often requiring the development of new legal framework, reporting standards and technological tools to address the unique characteristics of digital currencies. In this context, the rise of crypto-currencies not only challenges the operational effectiveness of tax administration systems but also raises broader concerns regarding financial transparency, revenue mobilization and the integrity of the global financial system (Dupuis & Gleason, 2021). According to Zhou and Zhiying (2023), crypto-currencies are generally described as digital or virtual forms of money that rely on advanced cryptographic methods for security and operate within decentralized networks. They enable individuals and businesses to carry out transactions directly with one another, without the

need for traditional financial intermediaries such as central banks. As a result, they often provide greater flexibility, including the potential for lower transaction costs and faster payment processing. Unlike fiat, crypto-currencies function as independent stores of value and are not issued or guaranteed by any central authority or government institution. They do not necessarily have a direct link to fiat currencies, yet they are widely used as a medium of exchange among both individuals and corporate entities. Additionally, crypto-currencies are distinguished by their ability to be easily transferred, stored, and traded through electronic platforms (European commission, 2018).

In Nigeria, the growing adoption of crypto-currencies can largely be attributed to declining trust in political institutions, the persistent weakness of the local currency, and rising inflationary pressures (Thankgod & Megheze, 2026). These economic and governance challenges have thus driven individuals and businesses to seek alternative stores of value and means of transaction outside the traditional financial system. However, the regulatory treatment of crypto-currencies varies significantly across different countries (Abdul, 2018). While some jurisdictions have embraced and permitted their use, others have imposed strict limitations or outright bans, reflecting differing policy priorities and concerns regarding financial stability, security, and control (Abdul, 2018).

The adoption and use of crypto-currencies therefore presents significant challenges for taxation due to the complex and decentralized nature of these digital assets. As emerging innovations in the financial market, crypto-currencies operate independently of traditional banking systems (Rajharia & Madhu, 2023), with smart contracts facilitating peer-to-peer transactions that are secure, transparent, and executed without intermediaries (Khan, 2023). Since the introduction of Bitcoin in 2009, numerous digital currencies and blockchain-based technologies have developed, expanding the financial ecosystem and creating novel opportunities for transactions and crowd funding through mechanisms such as Initial Coin Offerings (ICOs) (Grasic & Marko, 2024). While crypto-currencies offer advantages such as reduced reliance on intermediaries, enhanced financial access, and greater economic autonomy for users, they also introduce risks, including market volatility, unclear regulatory guidelines, and difficulties in aligning these transactions with conventional tax compliance frameworks (Thankgod & Megheze, 2026). In the context of Anambra State, the rapid growth of crypto-currency transactions raises critical concerns about how such decentralized financial activities can be monitored, recorded, and taxed effectively within the existing accounting and legal systems.

The current study therefore observed that the increasing prevalence of crypto-currency transactions in Anambra State poses significant challenges to tax compliance, as traditional accounting and taxation frameworks are often ill-equipped to address the decentralized, pseudonymous, and technologically complex nature of these digital assets. This study therefore seeks to investigate the implications of crypto-currency adoption on tax compliance from an accounting perspective.

1.2 Objective of the Study

The broad objective of the study is to examine the impact of crypto-currency transactions on tax compliance in Anambra State from an accounting perspective. Specifically, the study focused on the following:

- i. To assess the level of awareness and adoption of crypto-currency transactions among individuals and businesses in Anambra State.
- ii. To analyze the challenges posed by crypto-currency transactions to tax authorities and accounting professionals in enforcing compliance.
- iii. To evaluate the effectiveness of existing tax policies and regulatory frameworks in managing crypto-currency-related transactions in Anambra State.

2.1 Conceptual Review

2.1.1 Crypto Currency

Crypto-currency is a digital currency that is based on cryptographic techniques and operates on decentralized networks, typically based on blockchain technology. Unlike traditional fiat money, it is not issued or regulated by any central authority, making it widely independent of government control (Omaliko, 2026). The European Commission defines crypto-currency as a “digital representation of value” that can be transferred, stored, or traded electronically and accepted as a means of exchange (Ahmed, 2021). Similarly, the Internal Revenue Service describes it as a digital asset functioning as a medium of exchange, store of value, or unit of account (Katherine, Ruud, Shafik, & Michael,

2023). Crypto-currencies such as Bitcoin and Ethereum facilitate peer-to-peer transactions without intermediaries, enhancing efficiency but raising regulatory concerns. Their decentralized and pseudonymous nature poses challenges for classification, accounting, and taxation, as there is no universally accepted framework governing their legal and financial treatment across jurisdictions (Robin, Hui, Aiden & Lok, 2023).

2.1.2 Tax Compliance

Tax compliance refers to the extent to which tax payers adhere to tax laws, regulations, and reporting requirements established by relevant authorities. It involves accurate reporting of income, proper calculation of tax liabilities, timely filing of returns, and payment of taxes due. According to existing literature, tax compliance encompasses both voluntary compliance where taxpayers willingly fulfill obligations and enforced compliance driven by audits, penalties, and legal sanctions. In the context of emerging digital economies, tax compliance has become increasingly complex due to the rise of crypto-currencies and other digital assets. These assets introduce challenges such as valuation difficulties, anonymity, and cross-border transactions, which complicated tax assessment and enforcement (Lazea, Balea-Stanciu, Bunget, Sumănar, & Coraș, 2025). Furthermore, global initiatives such as the Crypto-Asset Reporting Framework aim to enhance transparency and improve compliance by mandating information sharing among tax authorities (Baer 2023). Effective tax compliance is essential for revenue generation, economic stability, and maintaining public trust in fiscal systems.

2.2 Empirical Review

Thankgod and Megheze (2026), explored the complex inter-section of crypto-currency and taxation with a specific focus on Nigeria. From a granular point of view, the study explored the challenges that governments face in levying duties on digital assets arising from the lack of uniform tax frameworks, challenges in tracing pseudonymous transactions, and valuation issues due to market volatility. The paper reviews current legal frameworks in key jurisdictions, including the United States, the European Union, and Nigeria, showing different ways of classification and approaches in taxation. These include the adoption of blockchain analysis tools, smart contracts to automate tax compliance, and international cooperation in standardizing tax rules across borders. The study concluded by emphasizing the need for clear regulatory regimes that are enforceable, while making a balance between innovation and fiscal responsibility.

Prabin, Prashamsa, Biplob and Nirmal, (2025) conducted a critical examination on the legal, institutional and regulatory frameworks governing crypto-currency taxation across jurisdictions, focusing on the inconsistencies, loopholes, and enforcement difficulties that hinder effective compliance and oversight. The study identified and analysed the key regulatory challenges, evaluated legal frameworks in selected jurisdictions, and provided recommendations for policy harmonization and improved compliance mechanisms. Using a systematic literature review of 40 peer-reviewed articles from 2013 to 2024, the study synthesized academic insights across legal, financial, and technological domains. Inclusion criteria focused on papers discussing crypto-currency taxation, DeFi, AML, and regulatory policy analysis. The review revealed fragmented tax treatment, limited enforcement capacity, growing use of DeFi tools to evade compliance, and the lack of international regulatory alignment.

Lazea, Balea-Stanciu, Bunget, Sumănar, and Coraș (2025) conducted a comprehensive bibliometric analysis of 182 scholarly publications to examine the evolution of research on crypto-currency taxation between 2002 and 2023. Drawing on data from the Scopus and Web of Science Core Collection databases, the study provided a structured assessment of trends, influential authors, and patterns of collaboration within the field. The analysis reveals that crypto-currency taxation is inherently interdisciplinary, spanning legal studies, fiscal policy, economics, and financial technology. Using analytical tools such as VOS viewer (version 1.6.20), Bibliometrix (version 4.0), and Microsoft Excel, the authors identified four dominant thematic areas: international tax frameworks and regulatory differences, classification and reporting of crypto-currency-related income, tax implications of emerging crypto assets, and compliance and enforcement challenges. The findings further indicated that tax treatment varies significantly across jurisdictions, with crypto-currencies subject to capital gains tax, income tax, or profit tax depending on the context.

Ahmed (2021) examined the nature and the legal status of crypto-currency by looking at the tax treatment of crypto-currency in some selected tax jurisdictions as well as the tax challenges posed by crypto-currency transactions. The study found that legal status of crypto-currency varies from country to country. The study also found that trading in crypto-currency is a peer-to-peer (P2P) decentralized transactions whereby the buyer and the seller transact and interact directly with each other without the intermediation by a third party.

3.0 METHODOLOGY

This section highlights the research methodology employed for the study. It includes, the research design, sources of data, data collection instruments, population of the study, sample size determination, sampling techniques, validity and reliability of the instrument and statistical tools for data analysis.

3.1 Research Design

Research design is a kind of blue print that guides the researcher in his or her investigation and analysis (Onwumere, 2009). The study adopted descriptive survey research design. Survey design is one in which a group of people or items are studied by collecting and analyzing data from representative, people or items considered to be representative of the entire group. It specifies how such data will be collected and analyzed. The rationale for adopting this design method is because it enables the researcher to solicit for information that might not be available on the pages of the text book.

3.2 Population and Sample Size Determination

The study employed judgmental sampling in selecting 70 Audit firms each from Awka and Onitsha bringing it to a total of 140 audit firms in Anambra state. Only one respondent was considered in each audit firm. In determining the sample size of this study, the Taro Yamane formula for determining a sample size from a finite population was used. The formula is stated below:

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2}$$

Where:

- n = sample size
- N = population (140)
- e = error Term (10% or 0.10)
- 1 = constant

Therefore, $n = \frac{140}{1 + 140(0.05)^2}$

$$n = 103.7 \text{ (Approx. 104)}$$

3.3 Sources and Method of Data Collection

Data for this study were gathered from both primary and secondary sources. The primary sources of data for this study were collected from structured questionnaires. This method of data collection was considered appropriate because it not only provided first-hand information needed for the study but also allowed respondents to make contributions to the work through their diverse views. On the other hand, the secondary sources of data for this study were obtained through the review of relevant literature and materials from text books, internet sources, journals, official reports, workshops and seminar papers.

Copies of the structured questionnaire were administered to respondents to elicit necessary information needed for the research. The responses were made to elicit objective rather than subjective information and to achieve this, the researcher employed the 5-point Likert scale which ranges from: Strongly Agree (5), Agree (4), Undecided (3), Disagree (2), Strongly Disagree (1). The researcher administered copies of the instruments directly to the respondents with the help of 2 trained research assistants. The distribution and retrieval of the instrument lasted for a period of two weeks.

3.4 Reliability of Instrument

To determine the reliability of the instrument, the ‘test-retest technique’ was used. The instruments were administered on a pilot sample drawn from ten (10) aware members of the public, all of whom are residents of urban areas, not included in the sample size. The pre-tests were carried out on two occasions with the interview guide, in an attempt to ascertain the reliability of the research instrument.

3.5 Method of Data Presentation and Analysis

One Sample Mean Z-test was utilized for the analyses of the two hypotheses formulated in this study, using the SPSS Statistical software IBM 26. The Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) has been deployed to pave more room for credibility of results obtained in this work through the analysis, leaving no room for error or doubt that is usually common in the manual approach. The hypotheses will be tested at 0.05 significance level.

$$\text{Mean } [\chi] = (5+4+3+2+1)/5 = 3.0$$

3.5.1 Decision Rule

For the questionnaire responses, a cut point of 3.0 was adopted as the criterion mean. This implies that any mean score that is 3.0 and above will be considered as Agreed/Acceptable while mean score below 3.0 will be considered as disagreed/Unacceptable. In the validation of hypotheses, the study will reject the null hypothesis if the probability value (sig.) is less than 0.05 (prob. < 0.05) otherwise, the study will fail to reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternate hypothesis.

4.0 Data Presentation and Analysis

A total of 104 questionnaires were distributed with the assistance of trained research assistants. Out of these, 100 (54 from Onitsha and 46 from Awka) were duly completed and submitted via our google Form, representing a response rate of 96.15%. Accordingly, the quantitative analysis of the study was based on the 100 valid and submitted responses. The sample of structured questionnaire is captured in Appendix 1.

4.1 Personal Data of Respondents

The personal data of respondents is given in table 1 below:

Table 1: Personal Data of Respondents

Variables		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Gender	Female	63	63.0	63.0	63.0
	Male	37	37.0	37.0	100.0
	Total	100	100.0	100.0	
Age	25-34	21	21.0	21.0	21.0
	35-44	54	54.0	54.0	75.0
	45-54	13	13.0	13.0	88.0
	55 and Above	2	2.0	2.0	90.0
	Below 25	10	10.0	10.0	100.0
Total	100	100.0	100.0		
Level	Junior	20	20.0	20.0	20.0
	Mid-level	15	15.0	15.0	35.0
	Senior	65	65.0	65.0	100.0
	Total	100	100.0	100.0	
Experience	1-5	26	26.0	26.0	26.0
	11-15	30	30.0	30.0	56.0
	16-20	4	4.0	4.0	60.0
	21 and Above	5	5.0	5.0	65.0
	6-10	35	35.0	35.0	100.0
Total	100	100.0	100.0		

Source: Field Survey, 2026

A total of 100 respondents participated in the study. The demographic characteristics of the respondents were analyzed using frequency and percentage distributions. The gender distribution indicates that 63% of the respondents were female, while 37% were male. This shows that females constituted the majority of the participants in the study. The inclusion of both male and female

respondents ensures that the study reflects diverse perspectives, thereby enhancing the credibility of the findings.

In terms of age distribution, the majority of respondents (54%) were within the 35–44 years age bracket. This was followed by respondents aged 25–34 years, who accounted for 21% of the sample. Those aged 45–54 years represented 13%, while 10% were below 25 years. Only 2% of the respondents were 55 years and above. This distribution suggests that most respondents are within their active working age, implying that they are likely to be economically engaged and sufficiently exposed to financial and technological developments such as crypto-currency transactions.

Regarding professional level, 65% of the respondents were senior-level staff, 20% were junior staff, and 15% were mid-level staff. The dominance of senior-level respondents indicates that large proportions of the participants occupy positions of responsibility and are likely to possess substantial knowledge of accounting practices and tax compliance matters. This strengthens the reliability of the responses provided.

With respect to years of experience, 35% of the respondents had 6–10 years of experience, while 30% had 11–15 years of experience. Additionally, 26% had 1–5 years of experience, 4% had 16–20 years, and 5% had 21 years and above. This shows that the majority of respondents possess moderate to considerable professional experience, which enhances their capacity to provide informed opinions on crypto-currency transactions and tax compliance issues.

Generally, the demographic characteristics indicate that the study is based on responses from experienced and professionally active individuals, thereby providing a credible foundation for analyzing the relationship between crypto-currency transactions and tax compliance in Anambra State.

4.1.1 Cronbach Alpha Reliability Test

To ensure the internal consistency of the research instrument, a reliability test was conducted using the Cronbach’s Alpha coefficient. The result, as presented in Table 4.2, shows a Cronbach’s Alpha value of 0.707 for the 15 items that made up the questionnaire.

Table 4.2: Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.707	15

Source: SPSS, version 26

A Cronbach’s Alpha coefficient of 0.707 indicates a good level of internal consistency among the questionnaire items. According to Nunnally (1978) and Tavakol&Dennick (2011), a Cronbach’s Alpha value of 0.70 and above is generally considered acceptable for research in the social sciences. Therefore, the instrument used for this study is considered reliable and suitable for further analysis.

4.2 Analyses of Research Questions

4.2.1 **Research Question One:** *What is the level of awareness and adoption of crypto-currency transactions among individuals and businesses in Anambra State?*

Awareness and Adoption of Crypto-currency

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	D	5	5.0	5.0	5.0
	U	25	25.0	25.0	30.0
	A	59	59.0	59.0	89.0
	SA	11	11.0	11.0	100.0
	Total	100	100.0	100.0	

Source: SPSS version 26

The analysis of responses on awareness and adoption of crypto-currency indicates that 59% of the respondents agreed and 11% strongly agreed with the statements relating to awareness and adoption of crypto-currency transactions. This implies that a combined total of 70% of the respondents expressed positive agreement regarding awareness and engagement with crypto-currency. On the other hand, 25% of the respondents were undecided, while only 5% disagreed with the statements. The low percentage of disagreement suggests that very few respondents lack awareness or exposure to crypto-currency transactions.

The findings therefore indicate a relatively high level of awareness and adoption of crypto-currency among individuals and businesses in Anambra State. The majority agreement suggests that crypto-currency is becoming increasingly recognized and possibly utilized within the state. However, the presence of 25% undecided responses imply that there is still a moderate level of uncertainty or limited understanding among some respondents.

In conclusion, the result suggests that crypto-currency awareness and adoption are considerably high, providing a relevant basis for examining its implications on tax compliance from an accounting perspective.

4.2.2 Research Question Two: *What are the challenges posed by crypto-currency transactions to tax authorities and accounting professionals in enforcing compliance?*

Challenges to Tax Compliance

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	U	17	17.0	17.0	17.0
	A	72	72.0	72.0	89.0
	SA	11	11.0	11.0	100.0
	Total	100	100.0	100.0	

Source: SPSS version 26.

The analysis of responses regarding the challenges posed by crypto-currency transactions to tax compliance shows that 72% of the respondents agreed and 11% strongly agreed with the statements presented. This represents a combined total of 83% of respondents acknowledging that crypto-currency transactions pose significant challenges to tax authorities and accounting professionals. In contrast, 17% of the respondents were undecided, while none of the respondents disagreed with the statements. The absence of disagreement indicates a strong consensus among participants that crypto-currency transactions create difficulties in tax administration and enforcement.

The high level of agreement suggests that issues such as transaction anonymity, difficulty in tracking digital assets, inadequate expertise, and poor record-keeping significantly affect tax compliance efforts. This finding highlights the complexity of regulating crypto-currency transactions within the existing tax framework. The result therefore indicates that crypto-currency transactions present considerable challenges to tax compliance in Anambra State, thereby reinforcing the need for improved regulatory mechanisms and professional capacity development from an accounting perspective.

4.2.3 Research Question Three: *What is the effectiveness of existing tax policies and regulatory frameworks in managing crypto-currency-related transactions in Anambra State?*

Effectiveness of Tax Policies and Regulatory Framework

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	U	1	1.0	1.0	1.0
	A	59	59.0	59.0	60.0
	SA	40	40.0	40.0	100.0
	Total	100	100.0	100.0	

Source: SPSS version 26

The analysis of responses on the effectiveness of existing tax policies and regulatory frameworks in managing crypto-currency-related transactions shows that 59% of the respondents agreed and 40% strongly agreed with the statements. This represents a combined total of 99% of respondents who expressed a positive view on the effectiveness of tax policies and regulatory frameworks. Only 1% of the respondents were undecided, while no respondent disagreed with the statements. This indicates a very strong consensus among respondents regarding the perceived effectiveness of existing tax policies and regulatory structures.

The high level of agreement therefore suggests that respondents believe that current tax laws and regulatory frameworks in Nigeria provide a reasonable structure for addressing crypto-currency-related transactions. However, the dominance of agreement responses may also reflect a perception that while policies exist, their effectiveness in practical enforcement may still require strengthening.

4.3 Hypotheses testing

4.3.1 Hypotheses Testing One

H₀₁: There is no significant awareness and adoption of crypto-currency transactions among individuals and businesses in Anambra State.

One-Sample Statistics

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Awareness and Adoption of Crypto-currency	100	3.76	.712	.071

One-Sample Z-Test

	Z	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
					Lower	Upper
Awareness and Adoption of Crypto-currency	52.781	99	.000	3.760	3.62	3.90

Source: SPSS version 26

The result of the one-sample statistics shows that the mean score for awareness and adoption of crypto-currency is 3.76 with a standard deviation of 0.712 and a standard error mean of 0.071, based on 100 respondents. This indicates a relatively high level of awareness and adoption among the respondents.

Meanwhile, the one-sample z-test result shows a z-value of 52.781 with 99 degrees of freedom and a p-value of 0.000. Since the p-value is less than 0.05, the result is statistically significant. This implies that the observed mean difference is not due to chance. Based on this result, we reject the null hypothesis and conclude that there is a significant level of awareness and adoption of crypto-currency transactions among individuals and businesses in Anambra State.

4.3.2 Hypotheses Testing Two

H₀₂: There is no statistically significant challenge posed by crypto-currency transactions to tax authorities and accounting professionals in enforcing compliance.

One-Sample Statistics

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Challenges to Tax Compliance	100	3.94	.528	.053

One-Sample Test

	t	Df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
					Lower	Upper
Challenges to Tax Compliance	74.567	99	.000	3.940	3.84	4.04

Source: SPSS version 26

The one-sample statistics show that the mean score for challenges to tax compliance is 3.94 with a standard deviation of 0.528 and a standard error mean of 0.053, based on 100 respondents. This indicates a high level of agreement among respondents that crypto-currency transactions pose significant challenges to tax compliance. The one-sample z-test result reveals a z-value of 74.567 with 99 degrees of freedom and a p-value of 0.000. Since the p-value is less than 0.05, the result is statistically significant, indicating that the observed difference is not due to random variation.

Consequently, we reject the null hypothesis (H₀₂) and conclude that there is a statistically significant challenge posed by crypto-currency transactions to tax authorities and accounting professionals in enforcing tax compliance in Anambra State.

4.3.3 Hypotheses Testing Three

H₀₃: Existing tax policies and regulatory frameworks is not effective in managing crypto-currency related transactions in Anambra State.

One-Sample Statistics

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Effectiveness of Tax Policies and Regulatory Framework	100	4.39	.510	.051

One-Sample Z-Test

	z	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
					Lower	Upper
Effectiveness of Tax Policies and Regulatory Framework	86.011	99	.000	4.390	4.29	4.49

Source: SPSS version 26

The one-sample statistics show that the mean score for the effectiveness of tax policies and regulatory frameworks is 4.39 with a standard deviation of 0.510 and a standard error mean of 0.051, based on 100 respondents. This indicates a very high level of agreement among respondents regarding the effectiveness of existing tax policies and regulatory frameworks.

The one-sample Z-test result reveals a z-value of 86.011 with 99 degrees of freedom and a p-value of 0.000. Since the p-value is less than 0.05, the result is statistically significant, meaning the observed mean difference is not due to chance. Based on this result, the null hypothesis (H₀₃) is rejected. Therefore, it is concluded that existing tax policies and regulatory frameworks are considered effective in managing crypto-currency-related transactions in Anambra State.

4.4 DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The findings of the study revealed that there is a significant level of awareness and adoption of crypto-currency transactions among individuals and businesses in Anambra State. This is consistent with the views of Lazea et al. (2025), who observed that crypto-currency usage has continued to expand globally across different jurisdictions, driven by technological advancement and increasing financial innovation. Their study also emphasized that crypto-currency adoption is influenced by evolving financial systems and digital transformation, which aligns with the present finding of growing awareness and engagement in Anambra State.

The study further found that crypto-currency transactions pose significant challenges to tax authorities and accounting professionals in enforcing compliance. This finding is strongly supported by Thankgod and Megheze (2026) and Prabin et al. (2025), who both identified major enforcement difficulties such as pseudonymous transactions, lack of uniform tax frameworks, valuation issues, and the use of decentralized finance systems to evade compliance. Similarly, Ahmed (2021) highlighted that the peer-to-peer and decentralized nature of crypto-currency transactions makes regulatory monitoring and taxation difficult, thereby reinforcing the challenges identified in this study.

Lastly, the study found that existing tax policies and regulatory frameworks are considered effective in managing crypto-currency-related transactions in Anambra State. This finding partially aligns with the empirical literature. For instance, Prabin et al. (2025) and Thankgod and Megheze (2026) emphasized that although regulatory frameworks exist in different jurisdictions, they are often fragmented and evolving, with many countries still improving their enforcement mechanisms. However, the present finding suggests that within the Nigerian context, respondents perceive current policies as relatively effective, possibly reflecting recent improvements in regulatory attention and policy development in the country.

The empirical literature therefore supports the study’s findings on awareness and challenges, while also providing a more critical global perspective on the effectiveness of regulatory frameworks, which appear to vary across jurisdictions.

5.0 Summary of Findings

The study examined crypto-currency transactions and tax compliance in Anambra State, Nigeria from an accounting perspective, drawing evidence from empirical analysis and hypothesis testing. Specifically, the study revealed the following:

- i. There is a significant awareness and adoption of crypto-currency transactions among individuals and businesses in Anambra State ($P < 0.05$).
- ii. There is a statistically significant challenge posed by crypto-currency transactions to tax authorities and accounting professionals in enforcing compliance ($P < 0.05$).
- iii. Existing tax policies and regulatory frameworks is effective in managing crypto-currency related transactions in Anambra State ($P < 0.05$).

5.1 CONCLUSION

This study examined crypto-currency transactions and tax compliance in Anambra State from an accounting perspective. The findings revealed a high level of awareness and adoption of crypto-currency among individuals and businesses, indicating its growing relevance in the financial activities of the state. The study further established that crypto-currency transactions pose significant challenges to tax authorities and accounting professionals, particularly in areas of transaction tracking, anonymity, and compliance enforcement.

However, the study also found that existing tax policies and regulatory frameworks are perceived to be relatively effective in managing crypto-currency-related transactions, although continuous improvement is necessary due to the evolving nature of digital finance. Overall, the study concludes that while crypto-currency adoption is increasing and regulatory structures are in place, effective tax compliance in this area requires strengthened enforcement mechanisms, improved technological capacity, and continuous policy adaptation to emerging financial innovations.

5.2 RECOMMENDATION

Based on the findings of the study, the following are three recommendations that align with each of the three findings:

1. **Strengthening Public Awareness and Education on Crypto-currency**
There is need for continuous public enlightenment by regulatory authorities such as the Federal Inland Revenue Service (FIRS) and professional accounting bodies. This will ensure that users and businesses are better informed about the tax implications, risks, and reporting obligations associated with crypto-currency transactions.
2. **Enhancing Tax Administration Capacity and Digital Monitoring Systems**
In response to the identified challenges faced by tax authorities and accounting professionals, government should invest in advanced blockchain analytics tools, digital tracking systems, and capacity-building programmes for tax officials. This will improve the ability to trace crypto-currency transactions, reduce tax evasion, and strengthen enforcement mechanisms within the tax system.
3. **Continuous Review and Harmonization of Tax Policies and Regulations**
Although existing tax policies were perceived as effective, the dynamic nature of crypto-currency requires continuous policy updates. Regulatory authorities should regularly review and harmonize tax laws to align with global best practices, ensuring clarity in reporting requirements, consistent classification of digital assets, and stronger enforcement frameworks to sustain compliance.

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APPENDIX 1: STRUCTURED QUESTIONNAIRE

Please respond appropriately by ticking the appropriate option. Mark the square bracket where necessary.

SECTION A: BIODATA

A. Gender

- i. Male
- ii. Female

B. Age

- i. Below 25
- ii. 25-34
- iii. 25-34
- iii. 35-44
- iv. 45-54
- v. 55-Above

C. Experience

- i. 0 - 5
- ii. 6 – 10
- iii. 11 -15
- iv. 16 -20
- v. 21 -Above

D. Level

- i. Junior

- ii. Mid-level []
- iii. Senior []

SECTION B: INVESTIGATIVE QUESTIONS

Kindly respond to the investigative questions to the best of your knowledge as this will enable us answer the research questions which guides the study. See the key below.

Key:

- SA** - Strongly Agree,
- A** - Agree,
- UD** - Undecided
- D** - Disagree,
- SA** - Strongly Disagree

Research Question One: What is the level of awareness and adoption of crypto-currency transactions among individuals and businesses in Anambra State?

S/N	AWARENESS AND ADOPTION OF CRYPTOCURRENCY	SA 5	A 4	UD 3	D 2	SD 1
1	I am aware of crypto-currency and how it operates.					
2	I understand how crypto-currency transactions are conducted.					
3	Crypto-currency is widely used among individuals and businesses in Anambra State.					
4	I have personally engaged in crypto-currency transactions.					
5	Crypto-currency is a convenient alternative to traditional financial systems.					

Research Question Two: What are the challenges posed by crypto-currency transactions to tax authorities and accounting professionals in enforcing compliance?

S/N	CHALLENGES TO TAX COMPLIANCE	SA 5	A 4	UD 3	D 2	SD 1
6	Cryptocurrency transactions are difficult for tax authorities to track.					
7	The anonymity of cryptocurrency encourages tax evasion.					
8	There is insufficient expertise among tax officials to handle cryptocurrency transactions.					
9	Accounting professionals face challenges in reporting cryptocurrency-related income.					
10	Lack of proper records of cryptocurrency transactions affects tax compliance.					

Research Question Three: What is the effectiveness of existing tax policies and regulatory frameworks in managing crypto-currency-related transactions in Anambra State?

S/N	EFFECTIVENESS OF TAX POLICIES AND REGULATORY FRAMEWORK	SA 5	A 4	UD 3	D 2	SD 1
11	Existing tax laws in Nigeria adequately address cryptocurrency transactions.					
12	Regulatory authorities have effective systems for monitoring cryptocurrency activities.					
13	Penalties and enforcement measures are sufficient to ensure compliance in cryptocurrency transactions.					
14	There is clear guidance on how cryptocurrency transactions should be reported for tax purposes.					
15	Improved regulations would enhance tax compliance among cryptocurrency users.					